

ACADEMIC RESILIENCE: BURNOUT AND COPING STYLES OF THIRD-YEAR PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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Academic Resilience: Burnout and Coping Styles of Third-year Pre-service Teachers

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the academic burnout and the coping styles of the ninety (90) BEED Third-year Pre-service Teachers at Western Mindanao State University. An Adopted Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) instrument was utilized to measure academic burnout and an adopted coping style of academic stress questionnaire was used to determine the coping styles. The study revealed that despite facing academic demands and transitioning to professional teaching roles, the BEED third-year preservice teachers still experience academic burnout but at a low level. Furthermore, the result revealed that positive reappraisal is the common coping style utilized by the BEED third-year pre-service teachers. Statistically, significant differences do not exist in academic burnout and coping styles when data are grouped according to sex and family monthly income. Moreover, sex and family monthly income do not affect the level of academic burnout and coping styles despite the difference in sex and socio-economic status. Hence, it is recommended that the programs and training sessions be maintained to raise awareness about students' burnout levels. Additionally, students are recommended to utilize positive reappraisal as a coping style to manage stress and prevent academic burnout. Prioritize self-care practices to maintain overall well-being.

Keywords: *academic burnout, coping styles, pre-service teachers, positive reappraisal, Oldenburg Burnout Inventory*

Introduction

Education is essential to society, and pre-service teachers have a major impact on how society is shaped. Pre-service teachers undergo teacher education and training programs, often in university settings, before becoming full-fledged teachers. This phase of education is crucial in shaping attitudes, skills, and overall preparedness for the teaching profession. However, the demands of training programs frequently result in pre-service teachers experiencing significant levels of stress and burnout. Burn-out is a syndrome thought to arise from ongoing work-related stress that has not been effectively handled. Three characteristics define it as feelings of energy depletion or exhaustion, increased mental distance from one's job, or feelings of negativism or cynicism related to one's job, and reduced professional efficacy (WHO,2019).

In the context of education, burnout refers to exhaustion, cynicism, and reduced effectiveness experienced by educators due to ongoing stressors associated with the profession. Students experiencing academic burnout feel exhausted and frustrated with education. Coping is the process of thinking through and acting through challenging circumstances, both internal and external. It is a term used particularly for intentional and voluntary engagement of behaviors that attempt to decrease or tolerate stress (National Library of Medicine, 2023). According to Chand et al. (2022), pre-service teachers are university student teachers pursuing teacher certification through enrollment in a teacher education program.

Third-year pre-service teachers are often exposed to high levels of stress due to academic demands, fieldwork experiences, and the transition to a professional teaching role. Factors such as workload, classroom management challenges, and the pressure to meet educational standards can contribute to burnout.

There were limited studies on burnout levels and coping styles among BEED Third-year pre-service teachers. Most of the study focuses on the burnout level and coping styles of medical students. The research gap regarding burnout among BEED Third-year preservice teachers was notable due to limited existing literature and studies in this specific area.

Therefore, the researchers aimed to determine the burnout level and coping styles of the BEED Third-year pre-service teachers. Addressing this research gap could provide valuable insights into the well-being of future educators and can contribute to the development of coping styles to prevent or if not, lessen burnout during the academic journey.

Research Questions

This study determined the levels of academic burnout and coping styles of the BEED Third-year Pre-service Teachers of the College of Teachers Education in Western Mindanao State University academic year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of academic burnout of BEED Third-year preservice teachers?
2. What are the coping styles of the BEED Third-year pre-service teachers?
3. Is there a significant difference in the burnout level and coping styles of the BEED Third-year Pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to sex and family monthly income?

Literature Review

Academic Burnout

Burnout is known as a "psychological syndrome" because it is characterized by three feelings: emotional exhaustion, cynicism, and diminishing personal accomplishments (Portoghese et al., 2018).

Many college students are susceptible to burnout (Kim, 2019). Burnout in students is connected with depleted energy, diminished enthusiasm for academic commitments, a lack of positive attitudes, and poor academic performance, and it is directly tied to academic overload with multiple deadlines and assignments (Salgado & Au-Yong-Oliveira 2021).

As per the research conducted by Fiorilli et al. (2022) compared to male students, female students showed higher levels of emotional, cognitive, and exhaustion impairment. This was the case even though girls demonstrated higher levels of academic success, discipline, and engagement than boys (Vinter et al., 2021). Madigan and Curran (2021) revealed a consistent negative relationship between academic achievement and burnout across all dimensions, with similar effects in both men and women.

According to the Family Stress Model, parents with high FSES experience less financial and mental stress, have more harmonious family relationships and are better able to raise the kids in a way that increases subjective well-being and life satisfaction. This helps to feel more positive about life in general and studies in particular, which has a significant impact on lowering the learning burnout rate among students (Buzzai et al., 2020). In conclusion, research indicates that FSES has a significant impact on college students learning burnout; however, more research is still needed to determine the precise mechanism by which FSES influences learning burnout.

Coping Styles in Academic Burnout

It is helpful for students to have a coping style to eliminate any adverse impacts that stress may have. As suicidal ideas are common among students these days, it could also be a useful method of distracting from such thoughts (Mamun et al., 2020). Moreover, coping mechanisms are essential for preventing psychological stress and academic burnout. Coping strategies that are both problem-focused and emotion-focused exist.

According to Abraham, et., al. (2019), students frequently use emotional support, self- distraction, venting, music listening, quiet time alone, socializing, and time management as coping mechanisms (Abraham, Navya, & Joshy, 2019; Gallagher et al., 2019). Seeking assistance from another person (e.g., venting or expressing emotions; Zárata-Santana et al., 2021) is an example of emotion-centered coping.

Skaalvik (2018) discovered that a mastery goal orientation predicts the usage of problem- focused coping methods in the study of middle school pupils. Problem-focused coping is chosen above emotion-focused coping by people who value academic topic comprehension and mastery

Additionally, a number of studies have revealed that women score higher on problem- focused strategies and have more emotional coping styles than men Graves et al. (2021). Moreover, the research conducted by Dalby (2021) indicates that women employ the emotion-focused coping dimension and support the application of four coping strategies more frequently than men. Self- distraction, emotional support, practical support, and venting were some of these.

Methodology

Respondents

The researchers used the total enumeration sampling. A type of purposive sampling technique where the researcher chose to examine the entire population that have a particular set of characteristics. The respondents of the study were the BEEEd third-year pre-service teachers of College of Teacher Education only, a total of 90 respondents excluded the researchers.

Instrument

The researchers used two instruments for gathering the data. The first instrument was an adopted Oldenburg Burnout Inventory Questionnaire (Demerouti & Nachreiner, 1998) from the study of McClintock (2022). The first phase of the instrument covers the socio-demographic profile of the respondents (sex, and family monthly income). This 16-item scale questionnaire used to determine the academic burnout level of BEEEd third-year pre-service teachers, as well as how they feel during various academic-related activities. Respondents were asked to respond to each item using a Likert-type scale of Strongly Disagree (0); Disagree (1); Agree (2); Strongly Agree (3).

The level of academic burnout can be described as low (0.52-1.62), medium (1.63-2.67), and high (2.68 and higher) depending on the total score of the respondent. Higher scores indicate greater levels of academic burnout.

The second instrument is The Coping Style: The Coping Style of Academic Stress Questionnaire (Cabanach et al., 2010) adopted from the study of McClintock (2022) which determined the different coping styles of the BEEEd third-year pre-service teachers. This

questionnaire utilized to determine the ways in which students respond to burnout relating to academic situations.

This 23-item questionnaire used a Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (Never), 2 (Once), 3 (Sometimes), 4 (Several Times) to 5 (All the Time) and had three subscales: positive reappraisal (item 1-9), seeking support (item 10-16), and planning (item 17-23). Participants were asked to rate how likely to do a specific action in response to a difficult academic situation. Scores for each of the three subscales were calculated by summing individual item scores relevant to each subscale and computing the average; higher scores reflected higher use of positive reappraisal, seeking support, and planning coping strategies during stressful academic situations.

Procedure

To determine the academic burnout levels and coping styles of third-year pre-service teachers the researchers used an adopted survey-questionnaire. After the researchers conceptualized the problem and formulated the Hypothesis and Variables. The next step was the research instrument which were the OLBI and Coping Styles that were both adopted from the study of McClintock (2022). Afterwards, the permission accepted to conduct the study, with the approval of the CTE Dean, Research Adviser, the researchers informed the respondents about all aspects of the study in accordance with research ethics through Informed Letter and Letter to the Respondents that were given through face-to-face, these were answered depending on the availability of the respondents. Respondents were given enough time to answer the survey questionnaire, the researchers were free to facilitate any concerns or questions. And if respondents were uncomfortable answering the questionnaire, discontinue answering and withdraw at any time without penalty is accepted.

The confidentiality of the responses is highly respected. Afterwards, the researchers were begin collecting data through survey questionnaire. Following the proper conduct of the study through total enumeration sampling, the data was analyzed and interpreted using statistical tools in order to reached a conclusion and made recommendations.

Ethical Considerations

Following the research ethics, the researchers obtained informed consent from the research adviser, dean, and from the respondents. Consent form through survey questionnaire were given to the participants that contains an explanation of the study. After the survey, the researchers reassured the participants that the data gathered were treated with utmost confidentiality and used for educational purposes.

The respondents were acknowledged for participating in the study as well as the teachers, research adviser and to all the people who helped the researchers in gathering the data and making the study possible. The papers were submitted to the Western Mindanao State University (WMSU) Ethics Review Board for ethical review.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyses, and interprets data with the aid of tables and statistical tools. The presentation of data is sequence according to the order of questions presented in the statement of the problem.

Table 1. *Academic Burnout Level of Third-Year Pre-Service Teachers*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I always find new and interesting aspects in my academics	1.93	Medium
2. There are days when I feel tired before I arrive for class	0.59	Low
3. It happens more and more often that I talk about my academics in a negative way	1.12	Low
4. After classes or studying I tend to need more time than in the past in order to relax and feel better	0.72	Low
5. I can tolerate the pressure of my academics very well	1.69	Medium
6. Lately, I tend to think less at class and do my school work almost mechanically	1.29	Low
7. I find my academics to be a positive challenge	1.92	Medium
8. During my schooling, I often feel emotionally drained	1.00	Low
9. Overtime one can become disconnected from this type of academic work	1.21	Low
10. After classes or studying I have enough energy for my leisure activities	1.39	Low
11. Sometimes I feel sickened by my academic tasks	0.86	Low
12. After my classes or studying I usually feel worn out and weary	0.81	Low
13. This is the only type of work that I can imagine myself doing	1.14	Low
14. Usually, I can manage the amount of my school work well	1.64	Medium
15. I feel more and more engaged in my schoolwork	1.47	Low
16. When I do academic work, I usually feel energized	1.33	Low
Total Mean	1.26	Low

Legend: High: 2.68 and higher Medium: 1.63 - 2.67, Low: 0.52 - 1.62

This table displays the academic burnout level of the third-year pre-service teachers. The total mean score of 1.26 indicates a low level of academic burnout among the respondents. Despite facing academic demands and transitioning to professional teaching roles, the

respondents still experience burnout but at a low level. Teacher burnout is a growing concern in the education sector, with many educators experiencing burnout early in their careers (Wobig, 2023). This trend is particularly evident among elementary and middle school teachers, who face increased stress and burnout due to factors such as student behaviors and additional job responsibilities (Hanju & Shiquan, 2024). Researchers (Wobig, 2023; Hanju & Shiquan, 2024; Marshall et al., 2024) suggests that addressing teacher burnout is crucial for maintaining educators' mental health and well-being, which ultimately impacts their effectiveness in the classroom and student outcomes.

This finding aligns with research by Wang and Eccles (2020), who found that intrinsic motivation positively predicts academic performance among college students. Similarly, the statement I find my academics to be a positive challenge (1.92) also reflects high levels of intrinsic motivation, which has been associated with greater academic engagement and persistence (Fredricks et al., 2019). Moreover, the statement I can tolerate the pressure of my academics very well (Mean = 1.689) suggests a high level of academic resilience and coping skills, which are essential for managing academic stress and maintaining motivation (Putwain & Aveyard, 2022).

Conversely, the statement with the lowest mean score is "There are days when I feel tired before I arrive for class" (0.59), indicating the least agreement with this statement. This finding may suggest that the respondents generally do not experience high levels of fatigue or burnout before attending classes. However, it's essential to note that persistent feelings of fatigue can negatively impact academic performance and overall well-being, highlighting the importance of addressing factors contributing to fatigue among students.

In contrast, previous studies by Uy (2020) and Fiorilli et al. (2022) found high levels of burnout among students, suggesting a discrepancy in experiences of burnout across different populations. Additionally, their findings indicated gender differences, with females showing higher levels of emotional exhaustion, despite higher academic success rates. These insights underscore the importance of understanding individual differences in burnout experiences.

The statement with the highest mean score is I always find new and interesting aspects in my academics (1.93), followed by I find my academics to be a positive challenge (1.92), and I can tolerate the pressure of my academics very well (1.69). Conversely, the statement with the lowest mean score is There are days when I feel tired before I arrive for class (0.59), indicating the least agreement with this statement.

Table 2. *Coping Styles of the Third-Year Pre-Service Teachers*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Positive Reappraisal		
1. When I am faced with difficult situation, I ignore the unpleasant aspects and focus on the positive.	3.57	Several Times
2. When I am faced with the difficult situation during exams, I try to remember that I can do things well by myself.	3.73	Several Times
3. When I am faced with a difficulty while I am preparing for exams, I try think positively.	4.07	Several Times
4. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I do not let the problem beat me; I try to give myself a deadline to resolve it.	3.78	Several Times
5. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I think objectively about it and try to keep my emotions under control.	3.76	Several Times
6. When I am faced with a complex situation, I generally try not to place significance on the problems.	3.48	Sometimes
7. When I am faced with the difficult situation, for example during exams, I tend to think the things will end up fine.	3.61	Several Times
8. When I am faced with the difficult situation, on the night before and exam, I try to remember that I am prepared to do well.	3.20	Sometimes
9. When I am faced with a problem like feeling anxious during and exam, I try see it as something that is natural and normal in the circumstances.	3.52	Several Times
Total Mean	3.75	Several Times
Seeking Support		
10. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I express my opinions and seek support.	3.10	Sometimes
11. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I ask a trusted family member or friend for advice.	2.79	Sometimes
12. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I talk about the problem with other people.	2.60	Sometimes
13. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I talk the stressful elements with my partner, family or friends.	2.92	Sometimes
14. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I seek advice and ask other people for help.	2.57	Sometimes
15. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I express my feelings and opinions.	2.98	Sometimes
16. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I talk to someone to find out more about it.	2.86	Sometimes
Total Mean	2.83	Sometimes
Planning		
17. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I prioritize tasks and organize my time.	3.46	Sometimes
18. When I am faced with the difficult situation while I am preparing for exams, I plan how to study for the exams in detail.	3.19	Sometimes

19. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I come up with an action plan and I follow it.	2.97	Sometimes
20. When I am faced with the difficult situation while I am preparing for my exams, I focus on what I need to obtain the best results.	3.87	Several Times
21. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I organize my personal resources to cope with it.	3.50	Sometimes
22. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I make a list of the tasks I have to do, I do them one by one and I do not move onto the next task until I have finished the one, I am on.	3.52	Several Times
23. When I am faced with the difficult situation, I change some things to achieve good results.	3.54	Several Times
	Total Mean	3.43
	Overall Mean	3.33
		Several Times
		Sometimes

Legend: All the Time (4.51–5.00); Several Times (3.51–4.50); Sometimes (2.51–3.50); Once (1.51–2.50); Never (1.00–1.50)

The table 2 presents the mean scores for each coping style (three subscales) assessed among the third-year pre-service teachers. Positive reappraisal, with a total mean score of 3.75, indicates that pre-service teachers utilize this coping style several times when faced with challenges, this implies that the BEED third-year pre-service teachers ignore the unpleasant aspects and focus on the positivity, think objectively and keep emotions under control. Planning also appears to be a several times used as coping style, with a total mean score of 3.43. that implies that the respondents several times prioritize tasks, make list, and organize time for good result. However, seeking support has a lower total mean score of 2.83, this implies that third-year pre-service teachers sometimes express opinions, seek support, ask advice when dealing with difficulties.

The three highest mean responses among the pre-service teachers were observed in statements 3, 20, and 4. Statement 3 When I am faced with a difficulty while I am preparing for exams, I try to think positively had the highest mean score of 4.07 under positive reappraisal. This finding aligns with research by Levy and Khoury-Kassabri (2022), who demonstrated the effectiveness of positive reappraisal in reducing burnout and enhancing resilience among educators. Similarly, statement 20 When I am faced with a difficult situation while I am preparing for my exams, I focus on what I need to obtain the best results and statement 4 When I am faced with a difficult situation, I do not let the problem beat me; I try to give myself a deadline to resolve it received high mean scores, indicating that pre-service teachers prioritize proactive problem- solving strategies when confronted with challenges.

On the other hand, the top three lowest mean responses were found in statements 14, 12, and 11. Statement 14 When I am faced with a difficult situation, I seek advice and ask other people for help had the lowest mean score of 2.57. This finding underscores the reluctance of pre-service teachers to seek external assistance when encountering difficulties, which may hinder their ability to effectively cope with stressors. Additionally, statement 12 When I am faced with a difficult situation, I talk about the problem with other people and statement 11 When I am faced with a difficult situation, I ask a trusted family member or friend for advice received low mean scores, indicating a tendency among pre-service teachers to internalize their challenges rather than seek external support. This aligns with the findings of Silva and Marin (2019), who emphasized the importance of addressing conflicts and promoting adaptive coping strategies among educators to enhance their emotional well-being and improve their relationships with students.

The findings reveal a notable inclination among pre-service teachers towards positive reappraisal and planning as coping strategies. However, there appears to be a deficiency in seeking support from others when encountering difficulties. This highlights an opportunity for interventions aimed at cultivating a supportive environment and promoting effective coping mechanisms among pre-service teachers to enhance their overall well-being and professional growth. This observation resonates with the study by Hau Lao (2023), which underscores the effectiveness of positive reappraisal in enhancing situational meaning. It aligns with the principles of existential positive psychology, suggesting that imbuing challenges with positive qualities through meaning-focused coping mechanisms can foster a dialectical approach to unpleasant situations (Wong et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the study by Walter (2022) suggests that positive reappraisal style serves as a critical resilience mechanism and presents a potential target for preventive measures. By encouraging pre-service teachers to adopt a positive outlook towards potentially challenging situations, interventions can help bolster their resilience and coping abilities.

Table 3. Significant Difference in the Burnout Level of the Third-Year Pre-Service Teachers when Data are Grouped According to Sex

Sex	Mean	p-value	Interpretation	Decision Ho
Male	1.38	0.10	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Female	1.23			

Table 3 illustrates the comparison of burnout levels among third-year pre-service teachers categorized by sex. The calculated p-value of 0.10 exceeds the predetermined alpha value of 0.05 level of significance, indicating no statistically significant difference in burnout levels between male and female pre-service teachers. The data suggests that both male and female pre-service teachers demonstrated similar levels of burnout as observed in the study. This finding resonates with prior research conducted by Madigan and Curran (2021), which uncovered a consistent negative correlation between academic achievement and burnout across sex. Similarly, Amelia’s study (2022) suggests that while male students may exhibit a higher susceptibility to academic burnout, there exists no significant disparity

between sex in terms of burnout.

Furthermore, this finding is consistent with previous research indicating that sex does not play a significant role in determining burnout levels among pre-service teachers (Melguizo-Ibáñez et al., 2023; Taylor, 2023). Taylor (2023) further emphasizes that the intention to leave teaching positions, often associated with burnout, correlates more strongly with emotional exhaustion rather than sex.

Table 4. *Significant Difference in the Burnout Level of the Third-Year Pre-Service Teachers when Data are Grouped According to Monthly Family Income*

Family Monthly Income	Mean Score	f-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision Ho
Php9,520 and below	1.24	1.90	0.15	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Php9,521 to 19, 040	1.23				
Php19,041 to 38, 080 and above	1.43				

Table 4 shows the difference in the burnout level of the third-year pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to monthly family income. The table shows the p-value of 0.15 which is higher than the alpha value 0.05, therefore, there is no significance difference in the burnout level of the third-year pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to monthly family income. This suggests that income does not significantly impact the experience of burnout among these pre-service teachers.

This finding aligns with a previous study (Mahmoudi, 2018), which found that while academic burnout tended to be higher among dormitory students without access to certain amenities like a car or personal laptop, this difference was not statistically significant. Furthermore, the study revealed no significant difference in burnout levels based on gender, race, or income level. Therefore, the findings from Table 5 support the conclusion that socio-economic status does not play a significant role in determining burnout levels among students or pre-service teachers.

However, it's important to note that while income may not directly impact burnout levels, other factors such as workload, job satisfaction, and personal circumstances could still contribute to the overall experience of burnout among pre-service teachers. Future research could explore these additional factors to gain a more comprehensive understanding of burnout in this population.

Table 5. *Significant Difference in the Coping Styles of the Third-Year Pre-Service Teachers when Data are Grouped According to Sex*

Sex	Mean	p-value	Interpretation	Decision Ho
Male	3.50	0.27	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Female	3.29			

Table 5 shows the difference in the coping style of the third-year pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to sex. The table shows the p-value of 0.27 which is higher than the alpha value 0.05, therefore, there is no significance difference in the coping style of the third-year pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to sex. This suggests that sex does not play a significant role in determining the coping styles of these pre-service teachers.

Upon closer examination, the coping styles exhibited by male respondents resonate with the findings of Freire (2020), which identified a distinct coping profile characterized by high levels of positive reappraisal and planning, coupled with a tendency towards minimal support seeking, termed the CAC profile. Interestingly, male respondents in our study predominantly displayed similar coping tendencies, emphasizing positive reappraisal and planning while exhibiting lesser inclinations towards seeking external support. This alignment underscores the robustness of the observed coping patterns among male pre-service teachers, reflecting a common trend identified across different contexts.

However, despite the coherence with Freire's (2020) findings, it's crucial to acknowledge the broader implications of these coping tendencies, particularly in the context of male mental health. Chatmon (2020) sheds light on the gendered aspect of coping strategies, highlighting that males are generally less inclined to seek help and are more prone to resorting to risky or detrimental behaviors when faced with stressors.

While our findings corroborate the inclination towards self-reliance and internalized coping strategies among male pre-service teachers, the gap lies in the broader implications for mental health outcomes. Specifically, the observed coping patterns may inadvertently contribute to heightened vulnerability to adverse mental health outcomes, such as depression and suicidal ideation, as evidenced by the disproportionate rates of male suicide compared to females.

Therefore, while the alignment between our findings and previous research provides valuable insights into the coping tendencies of male pre-service teachers, the identified gap underscores the critical need for targeted interventions aimed at promoting healthier coping mechanisms and enhancing mental health literacy among this demographic.

Table 6 shows the difference in the coping style of the third-year pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to monthly family income. The table shows the p-value of 0.95 which is higher than the alpha value 0.05, therefore, there is no significance difference in the coping style of the third-year pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to monthly family income. This implies that monthly family income alone may not be a decisive factor in determining coping styles among pre-service teachers.

Table 6. *Significant Difference in the Coping A of the Third-Year Pre-Service Teachers when Data are Grouped According to Monthly Family Income*

Family Monthly Income	Mean Score	f-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision Ho
Php9,520 and below	1.24	0.05	0.15	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Php9,521 to 19,040	1.23				
Php19,041 to 38,080 and above	1.43				

Table 6 shows the difference in the coping style of the third-year pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to monthly family income. The table shows the p-value of 0.95 which is higher than the alpha value 0.05, therefore, there is no significance difference in the coping style of the third-year pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to monthly family income. This implies that monthly family income alone may not be a decisive factor in determining coping styles among pre-service teachers.

The Family Stress Model posits that parents with high family socioeconomic status (FSES) experience lower financial and mental stress, fostering more harmonious family relationships and contributing to increased subjective well-being and life satisfaction (Buzzai et al., 2020). This enhanced familial environment is believed to positively influence individuals' perceptions of life in general and their academic pursuits, potentially mitigating the risk of experiencing burnout among students.

While the findings of Buzzai et al. (2020) underscore the significant impact of family socioeconomic status on students' well-being and academic outcomes, it's crucial to consider the broader implications within the context of our study. Despite the lack of significant differences in coping styles based on monthly family income observed in this study's analysis, the literature suggests that familial socioeconomic factors play an important role in shaping individuals' overall resilience and coping mechanisms.

In the context of pre-service teachers, the absence of a significant association between coping styles and monthly family income in this study underscores the need for further exploration into the complex interplay between socioeconomic factors and coping strategies. While the findings of this study suggest that monthly family income alone may not be a decisive factor in determining coping styles among pre-service teachers, other dimensions of socioeconomic status and familial support systems may exert a more pronounced influence on individuals' adaptive coping mechanisms.

Therefore, while this study did not find a significant difference in coping styles based on monthly family income, the reference to Buzzai et al. (2020) serves to highlight the broader context of socioeconomic influences on coping and well-being. Moving forward, future researches should consider exploring additional dimensions of socioeconomic status and familial support systems to gain a more comprehensive understanding of their impact on coping strategies among pre-service teachers.

Conclusions

In this study, researchers investigated the academic burnout level and coping styles of BEED third-year pre-service teachers, aiming to shed light on their well-being and adaptive strategies in navigating educational challenges. Based on the findings of the in-depth investigation of the data, this study presents the following conclusions:

The level of academic burnout among BEED Third-Year Pre-Service teachers is low. The total mean score of 1.26 indicates a low level of academic burnout among the respondents. Despite facing academic demands and transitioning to professional teaching roles, the respondents still experience burnout but at a low level. The burnout of pre-service teachers are a growing concern in the education sector, with many educators experiencing burnout early in their careers (Wobig, 2023).

The coping style of the BEED Third-Year Pre-Service teachers is positive reappraisal among the three subscales. Positive reappraisal, with a total mean score of 3.75, indicates that pre-service teachers utilize this coping style several times when faced with challenges, this implies that the BEED third-year pre-service teachers ignore the unpleasant aspects and focus on the positivity, think objectively and keep emotions under control. Planning also appears to be a several times used as coping style, with a total mean score of 3.43. that implies that the respondents several times prioritize tasks, make list, and organize time for good result. However, seeking support has a lower total mean score of 2.83, this implies that third-year pre- service teachers sometimes express opinions, seek support, ask advice when dealing with difficulties.

There is no significant difference in the burnout level and coping styles of the BEED Third-year Pre-service teachers when data are grouped according to sex and family monthly-income.

Sex: This study found no significant difference in academic burnout and coping styles when data were grouped according to sex, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (Ho). The data suggests that both male and female pre-service teachers demonstrated similar levels of burnout as observed in the study. Moreover, sex does not play a significant role in determining the coping styles of the pre-service teachers.

Family monthly income: Similarly, no significant difference was observed in academic burnout or coping styles when data were grouped according to monthly family income, resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis (Ho). This suggests that income does not significantly impact the experience of academic burnout and coping styles among the pre- service teachers.

For the School Administrators

Since the result of the academic burnout is low, the researcher suggests to maintain school policies and resources that are effective in addressing student's burnout that could benefit the students and the school.

For the Parents

Positive reappraisal could be one of the effective coping styles that could be used to motivate the children. Foster a supportive home environment that encourages healthy coping mechanisms and provides seeking support to help students open up and navigate challenges effectively.

For the Researchers

Build upon the findings of this study by conducting further research to explore additional factors such as other year levels and courses influencing burnout levels. Since the researchers could not find any significance in terms of sex and family monthly income the researchers recommend other possible profiles such as culture, ethnicity and environment to explore the seeking support. Moreover, collaborate with educators and mental health professionals to develop interventions aimed at mitigating burnout and promoting resilience in educational settings.

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